

significant difference between T1 and T4, which implies that yield reduction due to omission of insect control measures (T4) was not significant as compared with the other two components (see table). Nonapplication of fertilizer substantially reduced grain and straw yields in both cultivars. There was a significant difference in grain yield among varieties in 2001, but the variety × technology component interaction was not significant in either year. Maximum yield reduction was recorded with no fertilizer application, followed by no weeding and no insect control (see figure). Average yield data for 2 years revealed that the no-fertilization component reduced grain yield by 69% and 50% and straw yield by 67% and 43% in Vandana and Brown Gora, re-

Reduction in grain and straw yield due to nonapplication of technology components.

spectively; no weeding reduced grain yield by 50% and 45% and straw yield by 28% and 32%; and no insect control reduced grain yield by 14% and 6% and straw yield by 12% and 1%. The lower grain and straw yield reduction in local variety Brown Gora was due to its early vigor, weed competi-

tiveness, and low responsiveness to inputs. Grain yield was considerably low in 2001 as the crop suffered from moisture stress at the tillering, reproductive, and grain-filling stages. As reported by Yambao and Ingram (1988), the most severe moisture stress affecting rice yield coincides with booting to flowering /early grain filling.

Our study revealed that, among the technology components, fertilizer application and weeding control measures need special attention to achieve and sustain higher productivity in the rainfed upland rice ecosystem. Insect pest control should be implemented as needed.

Reference

Yambao EB, Ingram KT. 1988. Drought stress index for rice. Philipp. J. Crop Sci. 13:105-111.

Benefit-cost ratio in producing aromatic and nonaromatic rice genotypes in Kashmir Valley

G. A. Parray and Asif B. Shikari, Rice Research and Regional Station Khudwani, Sher-e-Kashmir University of Agricultural Sciences and Technology of Kashmir, J&K, 192102, India E-mail: ahmadparray@yahoo.co.in

Kashmir is well known for the cultivation of a large number of aromatic as well as nonaromatic landraces, which occupy different agroecological niches. Most of the aromatic rice varieties are local landraces maintained by farmers since time immemorial (now preserved at various rice stations of the university). Some of these varieties possess not only good aroma but also elite morphological features, which are desirable under our valley conditions. Of the aromatic genotypes, Mushk Budgi and Kamad are in great demand and are highly priced, whereas nonaromatic rice varieties

K-332 and Jhelum (SKAU-27) are commercially grown. Since a vast difference is found in the yielding abilities of these aromatic and nonaromatic varieties, there is room for improving these aromatic cultivars. A study was carried out to determine the benefit-cost ratio (BCR) of producing these varieties to better identify the factors that may need to be manipulated to further improve these varieties.

The cost of cultivation per hectare was Rs 18,334 for Mushk Budgi, Rs 18,226 for Kamad, and Rs 16,186 for the high-yielding commercial varieties Jhelum

(under valley basins) and K-332 (under high-altitude conditions) (Table 1a). The variation in the cost of cultivation was due to the different cost of seed—Rs 18 kg⁻¹ for Mushk Budgi and Rs 15 kg⁻¹ for Kamad as against Rs 6 kg⁻¹ for Jhelum and K-332. Moreover, an additional expenditure of Rs 1,540 was incurred when prophylactic measures were taken to control blast in the local cultivars. An estimation of net income and benefits and BCR showed that the high-yielding commercial varieties gave the highest net income of Rs 28,814 and Rs 16,214 under valley basin and high-altitude con-

ditions, respectively (Table 1b). Mushk Budgi performed better than Kamad, giving a net income of Rs 24,866 and Rs 14,066 under valley basin and high-altitude conditions, respectively, as compared with Kamad's Rs 15,374 and Rs 6,074. The highest BCR (1.78) was observed in Jhelum grown under valley basin conditions, followed by Mushk Budgi's 1.36 under the same conditions. K-332, which was recommended for high-altitude conditions, gave a BCR of 1.0. Mushk Budgi, under high-altitude conditions, gave a BCR of 0.77. Kamad had the lowest BCR values—0.84 and 0.33 under valley basin and high-altitude conditions, respectively.

It was evident that the high-yielding commercial varieties gave the maximum net returns and BCR under both conditions, followed by Mushk Budgi. An improvement in the yield of Mushk Budgi, through hybridization and selection of recombinants in advanced generations possessing good qualities of this variety (e.g., kernel size, milling percentage, head rice recovery, and aroma), will result in greater remuneration for farmers. There is thus an emerging need to improve the local aromatic landraces to develop varieties with high yield and aroma.

Table 1a. Cost of cultivation of high-value local aromatic rice and high-yielding commercial varieties.

Operation/input	Number/quantity required ha ⁻¹	Total cost involved (Rs ha ⁻¹)
<i>Power</i>		
Tractors	Three tillings	1,300
Puddling by bullocks	Four pairs	1,000
<i>Material</i>		
Cost of seed	60 kg Mushk Budgi	1,080
	Kamad	900
	Jhelum/K-332	400
<i>Fertilizer</i>		
Urea	145 kg	609
Diammonium phosphate	105 kg	903
Muriate of potash	37 kg	172
Weedicide (Machete)	30 kg	415
<i>Labor</i>		
Bunding	10 labor-day	450
FYM application	—	500
Application of inputs	2 labor-day	90
Uprooting of seedlings and transfer to transplanting site	15 labor-day	675
Transplanting	80 labor-day	3,600
Hand weeding	20 labor-day	900
Irrigation	15 labor-day	675
Harvesting	20 labor-day	900
Bundling of harvested produce	15 labor-day	675
Transporting to threshing floor	15 labor-day	675
Threshing, cleaning, and bagging	50 labor-day	2,250
<i>Control measures against blast</i>		
Seed treatment	200 g fungicide	140
Two sprayings	1,000 g fungicide	1,400
	Mushk Budgi	18,340
	Kamad	18,226
	Jhelum/K-332	16,186

Table 1b. Benefit-cost ratio (BCR) in producing high-value local aromatic rice versus high-yielding commercial varieties.

Agroclimatic condition	Cultivar/variety	Av grain/straw yield (q ha ⁻¹)		Gross income (Rs ha ⁻¹)	Total expenditure (Rs ha ⁻¹)	Net income (Rs ha ⁻¹)	BCR
		Grain	Straw				
Cultivation under Kashmir valley basin conditions (up to 1750 m)	Mushk Budgi	20	36	43,200	18,334	24,866	1.36
	Kamad	18	33	33,600	18,226	15,374	0.84
	Jhelum	50	75	45,000	16,186	28,814	1.78
Cultivation under high-altitude conditions (1750-2250 m)	Mushk Budgi	15	27	32,400	18,334	14,066	0.77
	Kamad	13	24	24,300	18,226	6,074	0.33
	Jhelum	36	54	32,400	16,186	16,214	1.00

Cost per unit of grain for calculation of net income and benefit-cost ratio.

Cultivar/variety	Cost of grain (Rs ha ⁻¹)	Cost of straw (Rs q ⁻¹)
Mushk Budgi	1,800	200
Kamad	1,500	200
Jhelum	600	200
K-332	600	200